

Liver PPI

Compare Outcomes Analysis

Introduction

TriNetX is the global federated health research network providing access to electronic medical records (diagnoses, procedures, medications, laboratory values, genomic information) across large healthcare organizations (HCOs). This report was run on the set of HCOs grouped into a network called Research. This network included 76 HCO(s).

This report describes a Compare Outcomes Analysis, named AIH Outcomes balance lab/med 1.13.23, generated by the TriNetX platform on Jan 13, 2023, 19:08:14 UTC. This analysis compared the outcomes of two cohorts: Cohort A (602 patients) named Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23 and Cohort B (1,189 patients) named Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23.

Methods

The analysis process includes two main steps: 1) Defining the cohorts through query criteria; 2) Setting up and running the analysis. Setting up the analysis requires definitions for the index event, outcomes criteria, and the time frame. Compare outcomes supports four analyses: Measures of Association, Survival, Number of Instances and Lab result distribution. These analyses have additional options that are listed in the Outcomes Definitions and Analyses Specifications section below. Furthermore, characteristics of the cohorts that are balanced using propensity score matching are also included in the Propensity Score Matching section.

Cohorts definition

This section lists all terms used in the definitions of the two cohorts.

Query Criteria for Cohort 1 (query name: Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23)

This query was run on the network Research with 76 HCO(s) queried and 76 HCO(s) responded. A total of 47 provider(s) responded with patients. The final cohort included 602 patients who matched the query criteria listed in the table below. For the text representation of the query criteria please see Appendix A.

Ungrouped terms				
must have	demographics	Age	Age (at least 18 years (most recent occurrence))	
cannot have	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:E83.01	Wilson's disease	
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:E88.01	Alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K83.0	Cholangitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.3	Primary biliary cirrhosis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:B15-B19	Viral hepatitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81	Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH)
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3	Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver
Group 1				
Group 1A Autoimmune hep				
must have	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4	Autoimmune hepatitis	
	and	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60	Unspecified cirrhosis of liver
date constraint	The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019			
event relationship	Any instance of No PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Autoimmune hep			

Group 1B No PPI				
must have	any of	medication	NLM:RXNORM:816346	dexlansoprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:283742	esomeprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:17128	lansoprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:40790	pantoprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:7646	Omeprazole

Group 2

Group 2A Autoimmune hep				
must have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60	Unspecified cirrhosis of liver
	and	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4	Autoimmune hepatitis
date constraint		The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019		
event relationship		Any instance of No liver decompensation occurred on or before any instance of Autoimmune hep		

Group 2B No liver decompensation				
cannot have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2	Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:A41	Other sepsis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0	Liver cell carcinoma
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K72	Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85	Esophageal varices
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7	Hepatorenal syndrome
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:R18	Ascites

Query Criteria for Cohort 2 (query name: Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23)

This query was run on the network Research with 76 HCO(s) queried and 76 HCO(s) responded. A total of 51 provider(s) responded with patients. The final cohort included 1,189 patients who matched the query criteria listed in the table below.

Ungrouped terms				
must have		demographics	Age	Age (at least 18 years (most recent occurrence))
cannot have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:E83.01	Wilson's disease
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:E88.01	Alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K83.0	Cholangitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.3	Primary biliary cirrhosis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:B15-B19	Viral hepatitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81	Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH)
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3	Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver

Group 1

Group 1A Autoimmune hep				
must have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4	Autoimmune hepatitis
	and	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60	Unspecified cirrhosis of liver
date constraint		The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019		
event relationship		Any instance of No PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Autoimmune hep		

Group 1B No PPI				
cannot have		medication	NLM:RXNORM:816346	dexlansoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:283742	esomeprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:17128	lansoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:40790	pantoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:7646	Omeprazole

Group 2

Group 2A Autoimmune hep				
must have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60	Unspecified cirrhosis of liver
	and	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4	Autoimmune hepatitis
date constraint		The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019		

event relationship	Any instance of No liver decompensation occurred on or before any instance of Autoimmune hep		
Group 2B No liver decompensation			
cannot have	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2	Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:A41
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K72
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7
	or	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:R18
			Ascites

Analysis Setup

This section contains the Index Event and Time Window definitions and a list of selected outcomes and the analyses.

Index Event & Time Window Definitions

The index event defines the point in time when each patient in the cohort enters the analysis. To define an index event for the cohort, one or more criteria for the cohort must be selected. The index date for each patient within a cohort is the day on which the patient first met the selected criteria for the cohort (listed in the table below).

As the index event defines the earliest time point after which outcomes are analyzed, the time window defines the duration during which outcomes are analyzed. The time window can start on the same day as the index event or at any specified time interval after the index event. The time window can end any time after the start date. Outcomes are defined as diagnoses, medications, procedures, or laboratory values that happened in the time window starting after the first occurrence of the index event.

Time Window Used in this Analysis

This analysis included outcomes that occurred in the time window that started on the same day as the first occurrence of the index event and ended 1095 days after the first occurrence of the index event

The index event only includes events that occurred up to 20 years ago. Patients whose index event occurred 20 years or more ago are excluded. In this analysis, 0 patients in Cohort 1 and 0 patients in Cohort 2 were excluded because they met the index event more than 20 years ago.

Index Events Used in this Analysis

Index events for the Compare Outcomes analysis were derived from the cohort definitions. Index events were defined separately for each cohort and were based on the criteria used in the original cohort definition. Please see Appendix B for the text representation of the index event definition.

The index event for Cohort 1 (query name: Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23) was defined as the following:

Group 1			
Group 1A Autoimmune hep			
must have	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4	Autoimmune hepatitis
	and	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60
			Unspecified cirrhosis of liver
date constraint	The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019		
event relationship	Any instance of No PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Autoimmune hep		
Group 1B No PPI			

must have	any of	medication	NLM:RXNORM:816346	dexlansoprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:283742	esomeprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:17128	lansoprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:40790	pantoprazole
		medication	NLM:RXNORM:7646	Omeprazole

The index event for Cohort 2 (query name: Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23) was defined as the following:

Group 1				
Group 1A Autoimmune hep				
must have		diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4	Autoimmune hepatitis
	and	diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60	Unspecified cirrhosis of liver
date constraint	The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019			
event relationship	Any instance of No PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Autoimmune hep			
Group 1B No PPI				
cannot have		medication	NLM:RXNORM:816346	dexlansoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:283742	esomeprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:17128	lansoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:40790	pantoprazole
	or	medication	NLM:RXNORM:7646	Omeprazole

Analyses Specifications

The Compare Outcomes Analytic supports four types of analyses: Measure of Association, Survival, Number of Instances, and Lab result distribution. The first three analyses support the “exclude patients with outcomes prior to the window” setting. This option can exclude patients from the analysis if they are not at risk for an outcome (e.g., if the outcome is a chronic disease). When "exclude patients with the outcome prior to the time window" is not checked, all patients in the cohort are included in the analysis, regardless of whether they had the outcome prior to the time window. When "exclude patients with the outcome prior to the time window" is checked, patients are excluded from the analysis if their record includes the outcome prior to the beginning of the time window. This selection will exclude all patients with the outcome prior to the index event. If the start of the time window for the analysis falls some days after the index event, patients will also be excluded if they have the outcome between the index event and the start of the time window.

Measure of Association Analysis

The Measure of Association Analysis calculates and compares the fraction of patients with the selected outcome. The output summary includes: Patients in each Cohort (count of patients meeting query criteria); Patients with Outcome in each Cohort (of the patients in the cohort, count of patients that had the outcome in the time window); and Risk (the fraction of patients in the cohort that have the outcome in the time window, i.e. Patients with Outcome / Patients in Cohort). In addition, Risk Difference (the difference in the risks in Cohort 1 and Cohort 2), Risk Ratio (the ratio of the risks in Cohort 1 and Cohort 2), and Odds Ratio (the ratio of the odds in Cohort 1 and Cohort 2). The bar chart shows the risk of the outcome for the both cohorts.

Survival Analysis

The Kaplan-Meier Analysis estimates probability of the outcome at a respective time interval (daily time interval is used in this analysis). In order to account for the patients who exited the cohort during the analysis period, and therefore should not be included in the analysis, censoring is applied. In this analysis, patients are removed from the analysis (censored) after the last fact in their record.

The output summary includes: Patients in each Cohort (count of patients meeting query criteria); Patients with Outcome (of the patients in the cohort, count of patients that had the outcome in the time window); Median Survival (the number of days when the survival drops below 50%; the “-” indicates that survival does not drop below 50% during the time window); and Survival Probability at End of Time Window (the % survival at the end of the time window). In addition, Log-Rank test, Hazard Ratio and test for Proportionality.

Number of Instances Analysis

The Number of Instances Analysis calculates how many times the outcome occurred in the time window. This analysis includes two additional settings: include patients with zero instances; the definition of an instance.

Selecting to exclude patients with zero instances will remove these patients from the calculations for mean number of instances, standard deviation, or median. The histogram showing the distribution of patients by number of instances will not contain a bar for zero. Alternatively, by selecting to include patients with zero instances, the mean, standard deviation, and median for number of instances will reflect these patients. The histogram will contain a bar for zero patients.

The definition of an instance affects how counts are analyzed. By selecting Date, each calendar date on which any of the terms selected in the outcome are recorded will represent one instance. For example, if the outcome is “Med A or Med B,” and a patient has “Med A” on January 3, then both medications on January 4, then “Med B” on January 6, then that patient is considered to have three instances— January 3, January 4, and January 6. Note that if an outcome occurs across several dates (e.g. Visit: inpatient encounter), then only the start date is tracked for the purpose of counting instances. A patient who begins at stay on January 1, ends that stay on January 3, begins another stay on January 10, and ends that stay on January 15, is considered to have two instances of the outcome.

Selecting Visit as an Instance will count any visit that includes the outcome as one instance, regardless of how many times it occurred. For instance, consider a patient administered an analgesic on each of the three days that make up an inpatient stay following some index event. If analgesic is an outcome, these three administrations will represent only one instance, because all three are associated with the same visit.

The output summary includes: Patients in Cohort (count of patients meeting query criteria); Patients with Outcome (of the patients in the cohort, count of patients that had the outcome in the time window); Mean (mean of the counts); Standard Deviation (standard deviation of the counts); Median (median of the counts); and Median (1+ instances) when patients with zero instances included in the analysis. In addition, T-Test statistics testing for the difference between the cohorts is included.

Laboratory Results Analysis

Lab Results can be included in the analysis only for the outcomes that are labs. Only the most recent lab values in the time window are included. For the lab results that are numeric, the outcome summary includes: Patients in Cohort (count of patients meeting query criteria); Patients with Outcome (of the patients in the cohort, count of patients that had the outcome in the time window); Mean (mean of the counts); and Standard Deviation (the standard deviation for lab values across patients in the cohort). In addition, T-Test statistics testing for the difference between the cohorts is included.

For the non-numeric lab results, three values are reported: counts of Negative; Positives; and Unknowns. The counts are represented in the bar chart as percentages of the total counts.

Outcome Definitions

Table below outlines the definitions for each outcome and the analysis specifications. For outcome definitions consisting of more than one term, at least one term must match. Please see Appendix C for the text representation of the outcome definitions.

Ascites		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:R18	Ascites
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Esophageal varices I85		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85	Esophageal varices
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Esophageal varices w/o bleeding I85.0		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85.00	Esophageal varices without bleeding
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Esophageal varices w/ bleeding I85.01		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:I85.01	Esophageal varices with bleeding
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Hepatic failure, not elsewhere specified K72		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K72	Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Hepatic failure, unspecified K72.9		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K72.9	Hepatic failure, unspecified
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Hepatorenal syndrome K76.7		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7	Hepatorenal syndrome
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Liver cell carcinoma C22.0		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0	Liver cell carcinoma
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Sepsis A41		
Outcome definition		

Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:A41	Other sepsis
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Sepsis Enterococcus A41.81		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:A41.81	Sepsis due to Enterococcus
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis K65.2		
Outcome definition		
Diagnosis	UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2	Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Mortality		
Outcome definition		
Demographics	Deceased	Deceased
Settings for the performed analyses		
Risk analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window
Kaplan - Meier survival analysis		including patients with outcome prior to the time window

Propensity Score Matching

Propensity score matching was performed on all listed characteristics. Characteristics of the cohorts before and after matching are summarized in the table below.

Cohort 1 and cohort 2 patient count before and after propensity score matching		
Cohort	Patient count before matching	Patient count after matching
1 - Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	602	477
2 - Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23	1,189	477

Propensity score density function - Before and after matching (cohort 1 - purple, cohort 2 - green)

Cohort 1 (N = 602) and cohort 2 (N = 1,189) characteristics before propensity score matching

Demographics

Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	AI	58.6 +/- 16.8	602	100%	<0.001	0.204
2	Age at Index	55.0 +/- 17.8	1,189	100%		

1	M	Male	101	16.8%	0.021	0.117	
2			254	21.4%			
Diagnosis							
	Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	I21	Acute myocardial infarction		19	3.2%	0.002	0.143
2				13	1.1%		
1	I50	Heart failure		53	8.8%	<0.001	0.191
2				49	4.1%		
1	I73	Other peripheral vascular diseases		22	3.7%	0.020	0.110
2				22	1.9%		
1	I63.5	Cerebral infarction due to unspecified occlusion or stenosis of cerebral arteries		10	1.7%	0.119	0.074
2				10	0.8%		
1	J44	Other chronic obstructive pulmonary disease		41	6.8%	<0.001	0.176
2				36	3.0%		
1	N18	Chronic kidney disease (CKD)		68	11.3%	<0.001	0.275
2				48	4.0%		
1	C81-C96	Malignant neoplasms of lymphoid, hematopoietic and related tissue		16	2.7%	0.021	0.108
2				14	1.2%		
1	I25	Chronic ischemic heart disease		70	11.6%	<0.001	0.218
2				66	5.6%		
1	E11	Type 2 diabetes mellitus		165	27.4%	<0.001	0.233
2				211	17.7%		
1	C00-C14	Malignant neoplasms of lip, oral cavity and pharynx		0	0%	0.024	0.130
2				10	0.8%		
1	C15-C26	Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs		19	3.2%	0.021	0.109
2				18	1.5%		
1	C30-C39	Malignant neoplasms of respiratory and intrathoracic organs		10	1.7%	0.119	0.074
2				10	0.8%		
1	C40-C41	Malignant neoplasms of bone and articular cartilage		10	1.7%	0.119	0.074
2				10	0.8%		
1	C43-C44	Melanoma and other malignant neoplasms of skin		16	2.7%	0.210	0.061
2				21	1.8%		
1	C45-C49	Malignant neoplasms of mesothelial and soft tissue		10	1.7%	<0.001	0.184
2				0	0%		
1	C50-C50	Malignant neoplasms of breast (C50)		17	2.8%	0.549	0.030
2				28	2.4%		
1	C51-C58	Malignant neoplasms of female genital organs		10	1.7%	0.400	0.041
2				14	1.2%		
1	C60-C63	Malignant neoplasms of male genital organs		10	1.7%	0.119	0.074
2				10	0.8%		
1	C64-C68	Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract		10	1.7%	0.119	0.074
2				10	0.8%		
1	C69-C72	Malignant neoplasms of eye, brain and other parts of central nervous system		10	1.7%	0.119	0.074
2				10	0.8%		

1	C73-C75	Malignant neoplasms of thyroid and other endocrine glands	10	1.7%	0.119	0.074
2			10	0.8%		
1	C76-C80	Malignant neoplasms of ill-defined, other secondary and unspecified sites	20	3.3%	0.189	0.064
2			27	2.3%		
1	C7A-C7A	Malignant neuroendocrine tumors (C7A)	10	1.7%	0.119	0.074
2			10	0.8%		
1	C7B-C7B	Secondary neuroendocrine tumors (C7B)	10	1.7%	<0.001	0.184
2			0	0%		

Medication

Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	4603	furosemide	181	30.1%	<0.001	0.583
2			96	8.1%		
1	9997	spironolactone	113	18.8%	<0.001	0.403
2			69	5.8%		
1	6218	lactulose	75	12.5%	<0.001	0.363
2			35	2.9%		
1	35619	rifaximin	44	7.3%	<0.001	0.320
2			12	1.0%		
1	8787	propranolol	36	6.0%	<0.001	0.243
2			17	1.4%		
1	7226	nadolol	28	4.7%	<0.001	0.182
2			18	1.5%		
1	20352	carvedilol	30	5.0%	<0.001	0.191
2			19	1.6%		

Laboratory

Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.	
1	9050	Bilirubin.total [Mass/volume] in Serum, Plasma or Blood	1.6 +/- 3.5	490	81.4%	0.164	0.081
2			1.4 +/- 2.4	668	56.2%		
1		1.30 - 0 mg/dL	209	34.7%	<0.001	0.264	
2			272	22.9%			
1	9045	Albumin [Mass/volume] in Serum, Plasma or Blood	3.6 +/- 0.7	448	74.4%	0.022	0.141
2			3.7 +/- 0.7	636	53.5%		
1		0 - 3.50 g/dL	299	49.7%	<0.001	0.456	
2			333	28.0%			
1	9032	INR in Plasma or Blood	1.2 +/- 0.5	430	71.4%	0.079	0.110
2			1.2 +/- 0.3	550	46.3%		
1		1.20 - 0 {INR}	205	34.1%	<0.001	0.305	
2			245	20.6%			

Cohort 1 (N = 477) and cohort 2 (N = 477) characteristics after propensity score matching

Demographics

Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.	
1	AI	Age at Index	57.8 +/- 16.8	477	100%	0.901	0.008
2			57.6 +/- 16.4	477	100%		
1	M	Male	85	17.8%	0.733	0.022	
2			81	17.0%			

Diagnosis

Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
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1	I21	Acute myocardial infarction	10	2.1%	1	<0.001
2			10	2.1%		
1	I50	Heart failure	34	7.1%	0.901	0.008
2			35	7.3%		
1	I73	Other peripheral vascular diseases	15	3.1%	0.558	0.038
2			12	2.5%		
1	I63.5	Cerebral infarction due to unspecified occlusion or stenosis of cerebral arteries	10	2.1%	1	<0.001
2			10	2.1%		
1	J44	Other chronic obstructive pulmonary disease	26	5.5%	0.886	0.009
2			25	5.2%		
1	N18	Chronic kidney disease (CKD)	35	7.3%	1	<0.001
2			35	7.3%		
1	C81-C96	Malignant neoplasms of lymphoid, hematopoietic and related tissue	10	2.1%	1	<0.001
2			10	2.1%		
1	I25	Chronic ischemic heart disease	41	8.6%	1	<0.001
2			41	8.6%		
1	E11	Type 2 diabetes mellitus	118	24.7%	0.544	0.039
2			110	23.1%		
1	C00-C14	Malignant neoplasms of lip, oral cavity and pharynx	0	0%	--	--
2			0	0%		
1	C15-C26	Malignant neoplasms of digestive organs	14	2.9%	0.691	0.026
2			12	2.5%		
1	C30-C39	Malignant neoplasms of respiratory and intrathoracic organs	10	2.1%	1	<0.001
2			10	2.1%		
1	C40-C41	Malignant neoplasms of bone and articular cartilage	0	0%	--	--
2			0	0%		
1	C43-C44	Melanoma and other malignant neoplasms of skin	10	2.1%	1	<0.001
2			10	2.1%		
1	C45-C49	Malignant neoplasms of mesothelial and soft tissue	0	0%	--	--
2			0	0%		
1	C50-C50	Malignant neoplasms of breast (C50)	10	2.1%	0.527	0.041
2			13	2.7%		
1	C51-C58	Malignant neoplasms of female genital organs	10	2.1%	1	<0.001
2			10	2.1%		
1	C60-C63	Malignant neoplasms of male genital organs	10	2.1%	0.001	0.207
2			0	0%		
1	C64-C68	Malignant neoplasms of urinary tract	10	2.1%	1	<0.001
2			10	2.1%		
1	C69-C72	Malignant neoplasms of eye, brain and other parts of central nervous system	10	2.1%	1	<0.001
2			10	2.1%		
1	C73-C75	Malignant neoplasms of thyroid and other endocrine glands	10	2.1%	1	<0.001
2			10	2.1%		
1	C76-C80	Malignant neoplasms of ill-defined, other secondary and unspecified sites	11	2.3%	0.825	0.014
2			10	2.1%		

1	C7A-C7A	Malignant neuroendocrine tumors (C7A)	10	2.1%	1	<0.001
2			10	2.1%		
1	C7B-C7B	Secondary neuroendocrine tumors (C7B)	0	0%	--	--
2			0	0%		

Medication

Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.
1	4603	furosemide	86	18.0%	0.508	0.043
2			94	19.7%		
1	9997	spironolactone	53	11.1%	0.760	0.020
2			56	11.7%		
1	6218	lactulose	30	6.3%	1	<0.001
2			30	6.3%		
1	35619	rifaximin	16	3.4%	0.443	0.050
2			12	2.5%		
1	8787	propranolol	15	3.1%	0.850	0.012
2			14	2.9%		
1	7226	nadolol	15	3.1%	0.558	0.038
2			12	2.5%		
1	20352	carvedilol	15	3.1%	1	<0.001
2			15	3.1%		

Laboratory

Cohort		Mean ± SD	Patients	% of Cohort	P-Value	Std diff.	
1	9050	Bilirubin.total [Mass/volume] in Serum, Plasma or Blood	1.4 +/- 2.6	379	79.5%	0.515	0.050
2			1.5 +/- 2.3	323	67.7%		
1		1.30 - 0 mg/dL	140	29.4%	0.573	0.037	
2			148	31.0%			
1	9045	Albumin [Mass/volume] in Serum, Plasma or Blood	3.7 +/- 0.7	343	71.9%	0.002	0.243
2			3.5 +/- 0.7	305	63.9%		
1		0 - 3.50 g/dL	206	43.2%	0.695	0.025	
2			212	44.4%			
1	9032	INR in Plasma or Blood	1.2 +/- 0.3	332	69.6%	0.225	0.100
2			1.2 +/- 0.3	262	54.9%		
1		1.20 - 0 {INR}	131	27.5%	0.773	0.019	
2			135	28.3%			

Results

Results are summarized in the table below. Analysis was performed on the cohorts after propensity score matching.

1 Ascites				
Risk analysis				
Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome		Risk
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	31		0.065
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	20		0.042
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.023	(-0.005, 0.052)	1.583	0.113
Risk Ratio	1.550	(0.896, 2.680)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.588	(0.892, 2.828)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis					
Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	31	--	92.78%	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	20	--	94.99%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	2.127	1	0.145		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.514	(0.863, 2.657)	0.944	1	0.331

2 Esophageal varices I85

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	26	0.055	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	24	0.050	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.004	(-0.024, 0.032)	0.291	0.771
Risk Ratio	1.083	(0.631, 1.859)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.088	(0.615, 1.924)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	26	--	93.54%	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	24	--	93.80%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	0.012	1	0.912		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.032	(0.593, 1.798)	0.058	1	0.809

3 Esophageal varices w/o bleeding I85.0

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	18	0.038	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	20	0.042	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	-0.004	(-0.029, 0.021)	-0.331	0.741
Risk Ratio	0.900	(0.482, 1.680)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	0.896	(0.468, 1.716)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	18	--	95.58%	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	20	--	94.78%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	0.223	1	0.637		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	0.858	(0.454, 1.622)	0.434	1	0.510

4 Esophageal varices w/ bleeding I85.01

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	0.021	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	0.021	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0	(-0.018, 0.018)	0	1
Risk Ratio	1	(0.420, 2.380)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1	(0.412, 2.425)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	--	99.76%	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	--	99.70%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	0.002	1	0.967		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	0.943	(0.059, 15.071)	2.042	1	0.153

5 Hepatic failure, not elsewhere specified K72

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	25	0.052	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	17	0.036	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.017	(-0.009, 0.043)	1.263	0.207
Risk Ratio	1.471	(0.805, 2.687)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.497	(0.797, 2.809)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	25	--	94.06%	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	17	--	95.73%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	1.296	1	0.255		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.428	(0.771, 2.644)	0.195	1	0.659

6 Hepatic failure, unspecified K72.9

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	20	0.042	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	13	0.027	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.015	(-0.008, 0.038)	1.240	0.215
Risk Ratio	1.538	(0.774, 3.057)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.562	(0.768, 3.178)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	20	--	95.17%	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	13	--	96.60%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	1.244	1	0.265		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	1.484	(0.738, 2.983)	0.421	1	0.516

7 Hepatorenal syndrome K76.7

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	0.021	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	0.021	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0	(-0.018, 0.018)	0	1
Risk Ratio	1	(0.420, 2.380)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1	(0.412, 2.425)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	--	99.55%	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	--	99.52%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	0.001	1	0.977		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	0.972	(0.137, 6.898)	0.840	1	0.359

8 Liver cell carcinoma C22.0

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	0.021	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	11	0.023	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	-0.002	(-0.021, 0.017)	-0.221	0.825
Risk Ratio	0.909	(0.390, 2.120)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	0.907	(0.382, 2.157)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	--	98.67%	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	11	--	97.18%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	2.549	1	0.110		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	0.433	(0.151, 1.247)	1.150	1	0.284

9 Sepsis A41

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	18	0.038	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	0.021	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	0.017	(-0.005, 0.038)	1.535	0.125
Risk Ratio	1.800	(0.840, 3.859)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	1.831	(0.836, 4.010)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	18	--	95.81%	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	--	98.41%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	5.587	1	0.018		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	2.896	(1.150, 7.296)	1.975	1	0.160

10 Sepsis Enterococcus A41.81

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	0.021
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	0	0
Risk Difference	0.021	95% CI (0.008, 0.034)	z 3.179 p 0.001
Risk Ratio	--	(--, --)	N/A N/A
Odds Ratio	--	(--, --)	N/A N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	10	--	99.71%
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	0	--	100.00%
Log-Rank Test	χ^2 0.923	df 1	p 0.337	
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	Hazard Ratio --	95% CI --	χ^2 --	df -- p --

11 Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis K65.2

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk		
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	0	0		
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	0	0		
		95% CI	z	p	
Risk Difference	--	(--, --)	--	--	
Risk Ratio	--	(--, --)	N/A	N/A	
Odds Ratio	--	(--, --)	N/A	N/A	

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	0	--	100.00%	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	0	--	100.00%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	0	1	1		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	--	--	--	--	--

12 Mortality

Risk analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Risk	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	45	0.094	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	48	0.101	
		95% CI	z	p
Risk Difference	-0.006	(-0.044, 0.031)	-0.327	0.743
Risk Ratio	0.938	(0.637, 1.380)	N/A	N/A
Odds Ratio	0.931	(0.607, 1.428)	N/A	N/A

Kaplan - Meier survival analysis

Cohort	Patients in cohort	Patients with outcome	Median survival (days)	Survival probability at end of time window	
1 Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	45	--	89.40%	
2 Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03- 19_1.13.23	477	48	--	87.78%	
	χ^2	df	p		
Log-Rank Test	0.320	1	0.571		
	Hazard Ratio	95% CI	χ^2	df	p
Hazard Ratio and Proportionality	0.889	(0.592, 1.336)	2.058	1	0.151

Appendix A – Text Representation of the Cohorts Definition

This section lists all terms used in the definitions of the two cohorts.

Query Criteria for Cohort 1 (query name: Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23)

Patients must have:

Age (Age) (at least 18 years (most recent occurrence)).

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

Wilson's disease (UMLS:ICD10CM:E83.01); or
Alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency (UMLS:ICD10CM:E88.01); or
Cholangitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K83.0); or
Primary biliary cirrhosis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.3); or
Viral hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:B15-B19); or
Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81); or
Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3).

All the following must be satisfied:

Autoimmune hep: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

all of the following:

Autoimmune hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4); and
Unspecified cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60).

No PPI: Any instance of No PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Autoimmune hep

Patients must have:

any of the following:

dexlansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:816346); or
esomeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:283742); or
lansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:17128); or
pantoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:40790); or
Omeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:7646).

Autoimmune hep: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

all of the following:

Unspecified cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60); and
Autoimmune hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4).

No liver decompensation: Any instance of No liver decompensation occurred on or before any instance of Autoimmune hep

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2); or
Other sepsis (UMLS:ICD10CM:A41); or

Liver cell carcinoma (UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0); or
Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified (UMLS:ICD10CM:K72); or
Esophageal varices (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85); or
Hepatorenal syndrome (UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7); or
Ascites (UMLS:ICD10CM:R18).

Query Criteria for Cohort 2 (query name: Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23)

Patients must have:

Age (Age) (at least 18 years (most recent occurrence)).

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

Wilson's disease (UMLS:ICD10CM:E83.01); or
Alpha-1-antitrypsin deficiency (UMLS:ICD10CM:E88.01); or
Cholangitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K83.0); or
Primary biliary cirrhosis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.3); or
Viral hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:B15-B19); or
Nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.81); or
Alcoholic cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K70.3).

All the following must be satisfied:

Autoimmune hep: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

all of the following:

Autoimmune hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4); and
Unspecified cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60).

No PPI: Any instance of No PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Autoimmune hep

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

dexlansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:816346); or
esomeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:283742); or
lansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:17128); or
pantoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:40790); or
Omeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:7646).

Autoimmune hep: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

all of the following:

Unspecified cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60); and
Autoimmune hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4).

No liver decompensation: Any instance of No liver decompensation occurred on or before any instance of Autoimmune hep

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2); or
Other sepsis (UMLS:ICD10CM:A41); or
Liver cell carcinoma (UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0); or
Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified (UMLS:ICD10CM:K72); or
Esophageal varices (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85); or
Hepatorenal syndrome (UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7); or
Ascites (UMLS:ICD10CM:R18).

Appendix B – Text Representation of the Analysis Setup

This section contains the Index Event definition for each cohort.

The index event for Cohort 1 (query name: Autoimmune Hep PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23) is defined as the following:

All the following must be satisfied:

Autoimmune hep: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

all of the following:

Autoimmune hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4); and
Unspecified cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60).

No PPI: Any instance of No PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Autoimmune hep

Patients must have:

any of the following:

dexlansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:816346); or
esomeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:283742); or
lansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:17128); or
pantoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:40790); or
Omeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:7646).

The index event for Cohort 2 (query name: Autoimmune Hep No PPI RN 4.03-19_1.13.23) is defined as the following:

All the following must be satisfied:

Autoimmune hep: The terms in this group occurred between Apr 1, 2003 and Jan 1, 2019

Patients must have:

all of the following:

Autoimmune hepatitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K75.4); and
Unspecified cirrhosis of liver (UMLS:ICD10CM:K74.60).

No PPI: Any instance of No PPI occurred within 3 months before or up to 3 years after any instance of Autoimmune hep

Patients cannot have:

any of the following:

dexlansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:816346); or
esomeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:283742); or
lansoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:17128); or

pantoprazole (NLM:RXNORM:40790); or
Omeprazole (NLM:RXNORM:7646).

Appendix C – Text Representation of the Outcomes Definition

This analysis includes the following outcomes:

Ascites

Patients must have:

Ascites (UMLS:ICD10CM:R18).

Esophageal varices I85

Patients must have:

Esophageal varices (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85).

Esophageal varices w/o bleeding I85.0

Patients must have:

Esophageal varices without bleeding (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85.00).

Esophageal varices w/ bleeding I85.01

Patients must have:

Esophageal varices with bleeding (UMLS:ICD10CM:I85.01).

Hepatic failure, not elsewhere specified K72

Patients must have:

Hepatic failure, not elsewhere classified (UMLS:ICD10CM:K72).

Hepatic failure, unspecified K72.9

Patients must have:

Hepatic failure, unspecified (UMLS:ICD10CM:K72.9).

Hepatorenal syndrome K76.7

Patients must have:

Hepatorenal syndrome (UMLS:ICD10CM:K76.7).

Liver cell carcinoma C22.0

Patients must have:

Liver cell carcinoma (UMLS:ICD10CM:C22.0).

Sepsis A41

Patients must have:

Other sepsis (UMLS:ICD10CM:A41).

Sepsis Enterococcus A41.81

Patients must have:

Sepsis due to Enterococcus (UMLS:ICD10CM:A41.81).

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis K65.2

Patients must have:

Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis (UMLS:ICD10CM:K65.2).

Mortality

Patients must have:

Deceased (Deceased).